

Original Research Article

Is Mathematics Emotional? Poetry as an Affective Activity in Humanistic Mathematics Learning

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ABSTRACT: Can mathematics be as humanistic and emotional as poetry, and how do mathematics and students' emotions intersect? Building on previous scholarship that views both mathematics and poetry as forms of humanistic expression, this article explored how the practice of writing mathematical poetry can benefit introductory college classrooms by emphasizing the connection between students' emotions and their learning in mathematics. The study analyzed two examples of mathematical poetry written by college algebra students, using The Listening Guide Method. The findings demonstrated that students' emotions contributed to the creation of meaningful mathematical work that connects to their passion and personal lived experiences. This article recommends mathematical poetry writing in college algebra classrooms as a humanistic approach because it helps students recognize the vitality of mathematics and find joy in their mathematical endeavors.

KEYWORDS: *emotions, mathematical poetry, college algebra, The Listening Guide, humanistic approach to mathematics education*

"I don't like math. I like reading." "I want to be a kindergarten teacher. Why do I need this class?" I hear in my college students' comments that this required algebra class makes them fearful, frustrated, and anxious. I hear their negative feelings of math and their perceptions of its coldness and irrelevance to their lives; sometimes in the same class meeting. I also hear their hobbies, passions, and beautiful stories about life outside the math classroom. What if we gave students the opportunity to connect math with their own stories? Can math be joyfully emotional in its connection to the things that they are passionate about?

With this question in mind, I assigned a final project that gave students the freedom to use all of the math they learned to solve problems that they were passionate about. To make the final project even more celebratory, I also invited them to optionally include creative writing, videos, or performances alongside their math work. Several students chose to write poetry. Their poems have stayed with me since I first read them, later provoking the wondering: Can mathematics be as humanistic and emotional as poetry? How do mathematics and students' emotions intersect?

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The Emotional Facet of Doing Mathematics

Mathematics is inherently different from poetry because it is a more structured system of knowledge with a defined framework. However, the *process of doing mathematics* can evoke a level of emotional involvement similar to that of poetry. For example, I often recall nostalgic moments while doing math. When I encountered the multiplicative inverse of matrices during my graduate studies, I couldn't help but cast my mind back to when my college friends and I tackled elementary linear algebra problems in the library, writing math all over the board in the cool fall weather of Athens, Georgia. After many years, when those friends and I met, we could still vividly remember those days of doing math together. It's remarkable how the emotions associated with math can transcend time and space, traveling with us whenever we encounter the same mathematics later in life.

Connecting Mathematics and Poetry

Beyond evoking memorable moments, the *process of doing mathematics* can become intertwined with people's passions and personal stories. It is important to recognize that humans exist within a complex ecological system (Bronfenbrenner, 1977/1979), and human beings carry their stories and emotions with them wherever they go, including the mathematics classroom. With this in mind, I continued to ponder my journey of encouraging students to form connections with mathematics by relating it to their own stories. When students were asked to use mathematics to express the world they experience, they voluntarily infused mathematics with emotional stories—writing poetry along with their mathematical work. This experimental teaching practice of inviting students to write poetry which embraces emotions as mediators for engaging mathematics is just the beginning of my vision for a humanistic approach to introductory college mathematics classrooms (Figure 1).

Fig. 1. A Humanistic Approach to Connecting Emotions and Mathematics Through Poetry

Beyond the Elementary School Pedagogy of Mathematical Poetry

Writing mathematical poetry in classrooms is considered a recent pedagogy in humanistic mathematics in the realm of mathematics education (Campos & Saraiva, 2019). As Karaali (2014) states, “Mathematical poetry is a perfect model and ambassador for a more humanistic understanding of mathematics” (p. 38). Scholars have argued that exploration and articulation of mathematical ideas for young children may benefit from usage of humanistic language in mathematical poetry, such as metaphor and analogy, as alternative to scientific language (i.e.,

formulas and symbols) (Pimm, 1981; Campos & Saraiva, 2019). For example, Triandafillidis (2006) describes a case where children from 8 to 10 years old wrote mathematical poetry in which multiplication and division were portrayed as human characters, finding that the stories in their poetry demonstrated the children's understanding of these two operations. In another study, first graders explored the concepts of money (coins and notes) and prices through a Circular Poem that was presented to them by their teachers (Campos & Saraiva, 2019).

Clearly, mathematical poetry has powerful potential in elementary classrooms from a humanistic mathematics perspective. However, introductory college mathematics classrooms (e.g. a math-for-liberal-arts course) have many differences from the elementary setting. There, mathematical poetry as a pedagogy in introductory college mathematics classrooms demands further explorations. How does mathematical poetry uniquely contribute to introductory college classrooms as an essential, even indispensable, humanistic pedagogical approach? Expanding on previous interdisciplinary research on poetry writing in college mathematics education (e.g., Karaali 2014; Staats, 2014), I chose to utilize the Listening Guide method (e.g., Gillian et al., 2006; Helme, 2021) to further investigate students' emotions as conveyed through mathematical poetry.

The Listening Guide Method

The Listening Guide, developed in the field of psychology, is a qualitative research method that allows researchers to systematically analyze participants' internal landscapes (Gilligan, 2015; Gilligan et al., 2003). It was originally designed for researchers to analyze interviews through a multi-stage process that examines certain emotional features (Gilligan et al., 2003). Although this method has widely been utilized to analyze young mothers' emotional state during postpartum (Mauthner, 2002), its framework can be applied in other contexts, including the current college algebra focus. In this study, I used a modified version of the Listening Guide, accommodating the fact that, rather than interviewing participants, I "listened" to their voices by closely reading their written mathematical poetry. In my analysis, I explored (1) their emotional experiences as learners of mathematics and (2) how these experiences related to their personal perspectives and societal influences. Throughout the process, I completed multiple stages of listening, taking into account the various facets of their distinct voices.

After listening to the larger context and overall plot in the first stage, I made modifications to the second stage of the Listening Guide. Typically, researchers extract the first-person pronoun from the interview script and create an 'I poem' (e.g., Gilligan et al., 2003) for analysis. Other researchers expand the Listening Guide and develop a 'They poem' to focus on narratives from individuals such as teachers discussing their students in the third person (e.g., Helme, 2022). In my study, I no longer needed to create a poem since my students had already written mathematical poetry. However, I did identify pronouns and analyze each mathematical poem by sections, creating a 'We poem' and an 'It poem' (i.e., when an object serves as the protagonist). My next step was to listen and re-listen to my students' original poetry or small portions of it, paying attention to the pronouns, verbs, rhythm, repetition, and tone. These elements assisted me in interpreting my students' emotions. Finally, in the last stage of my listening process, I connected my students' emotions and their emotional stories from the poetry to their mathematical work, and then I composed my final analysis. Following Gilligan et al. (2003), I not only focused on listening to the mathematical poetry, but actively incorporated my personal feelings and responses into the interpretation process. This ensured that my subjectivities were acknowledged and actively involved in the overall analysis.

Data Analysis

Artifacts

I selected and focused on two mathematical poems written by students from my college algebra class². Both students related to their personal experiences and conveyed their emotions in their poetry. Student A's poem (Appendix 1) includes mathematical language, while Student B's poem (Appendix 1) solely focuses on her feelings and stories.

Student A's poem

As we know the war on drugs took a toll on us
 After the '70s, from '80 to '99, black people did more and more jail time
 We doubled the percentage in such a short bit
 We've seen how it hits and it's truly not sublime

2008 we took a win when Obama became our president
 We had so much reduction 'cause we saw us in him
 The rates have gone down, and covid reduced them greatly
 But not without cost if you're around age 80

So dark and hard to swallow 'cause my government is shady
 And this is random but it's harder if you happen to be a lady
 Maybe not so much regarding prison, but there's babies
 9 months of carrying for him to be pushed down so greatly

The system feels awful when you've always got to fight it
 Like Floyd in 2020 when the riots were incited
 Tens of thousands were arrested so we could be silenced
 So yes. My passion for this flame has caused me to ignite it

Plot analysis. The overall plot is laid out in multiple scenes across four verses in Student A's poem, and I describe the theme as finding hope amidst despair. The plot proceeds in chronological order and is situated in a society experiencing ongoing violence, especially affecting African Americans. Even following the civil rights movement in the 1960's, Black people have been systemically oppressed and disproportionately targeted by policing and the prison-industrial complex (Hattery & Smith, 2018). From this despair a hope arose with the election of President Obama, inspiring many young Black men to look up to him. Soon thereafter, the COVID-19 pandemic concealed the ongoing disproportionate imprisonment faced by Black people, whereas the murder of George Floyd served as a reminder that anti-Black state violence still persists. The story also explores the destiny of the elder generation and the role of women in raising their children. Identifying as an African American man, Student A's drive to make the voices of Black people heard fuels his journey.

Connecting Emotions to Linear Functions. To further analyze Student A's emotions, I constructed a "We poem":

We know the war on drugs took a toll on us
We doubled the percentage in such a short bit

² Both poems are presented with permission of the students.

We've seen how it hits and it's truly not sublime
we took a win when Obama became our president
We had so much reduction 'cause we saw us in him
 Tens of thousands were arrested so we could be silenced

The "We poem" is designed to emphasize the emotions of Student A seeing himself as a member of the African American community. Viewing the "we" statements reveals feelings strongly connected to his social identity. In the meantime, I noticed that Student A incorporated pronouns other than "we" in his poetry, including a shift from the active to the passive voice ("be silenced"). As a result, I organized an "It poem" along with the "We poem" to expand the analysis of Student A's emotions:

The rates have gone down
covid reduced them greatly
 So dark and hard to swallow 'cause my government is shady
The system feels awful
 Like Floyd in 2020 when the riots were incited

In the "We poem," Student A expressed strong emotions associated with the experiences of Black people, using action verbs such as "know," "see" (in both past and present tenses), and "take" (in the past tense). The emotions stemming from the past are multifaceted. On one hand, Student A experienced frustration because the Black community is well aware ("know" and "have seen") of how the War on Drugs has devastated them materially and spiritually and "taken a toll" on their well-being. On the other hand, there is a sense of excitement and empowerment within the Black community as they unite to combat systemic oppression, as they can envision themselves reflected in President Obama's success. In the "It poem," noting that the COVID pandemic had resulted in a decrease in incarceration rates (Carson et al, 2022), Student A developed a sense of optimism and relative tranquility. His tone shifted to outrage as he revealed disturbing facts about the "shady" government and the injustice surrounding George Floyd. He also expressed empathy for the elderly and women, as they constantly had to battle against the "awful" system. Now, not only do the elderly and women have to fight for their rights (and lives), but also Student A was deeply affected by the riots sparked by Floyd's death in 2020 and has decided not to remain silent, concluding his poem by stating "My passion for this flame has caused me to ignite it."

The emotionality in Student A's writing is better understood when considering the context of his chosen mathematical project. Connecting with his passion for advocating for the African American community, Student A researched data and developed a line of best fit to estimate the percentage of Black men aged 22-30 who would be incarcerated by 2025. Some key data points in his math work were from the years 1980, 1990, 1995, and 1999. During this period, the incarceration rate for Black men in this age group increased from 16% in 1980 to 32.8% in 1999. In his poem, he expressed this by saying, "After the '70s, from '80 to '99, black people did more and more jail time. We doubled the percentage in such a short bit." Additionally, in his mathematical analysis, he considered why his line of best fit, based on previous data, might not be accurate. Firstly, he did not believe that the rate of change would be doubled again in the coming years, as society has undergone drastic changes and unexpected events described in his poem, such as Obama becoming the U.S. president, George Floyd's murder, and the pandemic, which would continue to impact the Black community. He also acknowledged the impact that

the societal system would have on the incarceration rate of young African American males, expressing his emotions about the current system in his poetry.

Student B's poem

Family turns their passion into business
 But money bleeds out into the gutter
 Floors are failing and paint is chipping
 How can the business rise again?

Warm drinks and greetings
 Holiday presents flow out the door
 Fresh coats of paints and floors made for dancing
 Family shines with success

Plot analysis. I plotted two distinct scenes of Student B's poem. In the first verse, the buildings were surrounded by a nostalgic yet muted atmosphere, as they retained remnants of the past. The scene reminded me of the times when I used to stand in front of historic buildings in Stillwater, Minnesota. With the presence of aged paintings, I felt a connection to the passage of time and a strong sense of nostalgia. Conversely, in the second scene, the atmosphere was saturated with the sounds of laughter. Families gathered in a vibrant and dazzling restaurant, adorned with radiant lights and festive ornaments, to celebrate the holiday season.

As a young college student who has supported her studies by working in a distillery in Stillwater every weekend, Student B has witnessed the unfortunate challenges faced by a small family business and has strived to create change. Meanwhile, the richness and complexity of the scenes demonstrate the fluidity of their emotions as conveyed through the poem. To further explore these emotions, I followed the second step of The Listening Guide and investigated Student B's emotions based on pronoun usage.

Connecting emotions to data analysis. Student B humanized the objects in both verses of her poem. To gain a better understanding of Student B's emotions, I analyzed her poem through the lens of an "It poem," which focused on the pronouns and verbs along with them:

But Family turns their passion into business
 money bleeds out into the gutter
 Floors are failing and paint is chipping
 How can the business rise again?

Warm drinks and greetings
Holiday presents flow out the door
 Fresh coats of paints and floors made for dancing
Family shines with success

Through the "It poem," it is clear that in both verses, Student B humanized the objects. Money "bleeds out" just like uncontrollable rainwater, and the floors are "failing" and the paint is "chipping" in an old building. Through these vivid descriptions, she conveyed a sense of deep sorrow and disappointment from witnessing the destruction of small family businesses. However, Student B's motivation stemmed from the dedication and passion shown by these families in starting their businesses. She asked herself, "How can the business rise again?" In the

second stanza, Student B described the joyful holiday scenes with her newfound enlightenment and excitement. She portrayed the image of presents "flowing out of the door" and floors "dancing," as if they were exuberant children eagerly anticipating their favorite outdoor activities. Ultimately, Student B managed to cope with her sorrow and transformed disappointment into hope and aspiration for the future, symbolized by family shining with success.

What caused Student B to change her emotion from sadness to endless hope? I viewed Student B's math work as a connection between these two contrasting emotions. Student B was employed at a distillery in Stillwater to fund her college education. Transitioning from the frustration of witnessing the challenges faced by the family business, she turned her attention to her future aspiration of restoring the distillery in the historical building. In order to achieve this goal, Student B assessed the necessary repairs for the distillery and determined the amount of profit required to cover these expenses. She analyzed labor, materials, overhead costs, and employee wages using mathematical calculations to determine the time it would take to regain the repair costs and identify strategies to maximize our profit.

She started from assessing cost for employees because this family business is proud of paying their employees more than a typical wage for working at a bar. Student B made a chart (Figure 2) which represents the wages of each employee, and hours they work during a week.

Fig. 2. Employee wages chart by Student B

Fig. 3. Cocktail costs chart by Student B

As Student B progressed, she also realized that she needed to seek balance between social issues (e.g. protection of historical buildings, fair wages for part-time hourly workers, sustainability of small family-owned businesses) and the costs to cover the repairs (technical issues using mathematics). The distillery owners and Student B have decided to use leftover grain from local farms for their distilling process. To cover the expenses for a new outside deck, they further examined the cost of their cocktail products (Figure 3). They aimed to cover major repairs while still making profits after two months.

Discussion

Having had students write poetry while engaging in math, I wondered what mathematical poetry was. The editors of *Against Infinity* defined mathematical poetry as "an association of mathematical concepts, relationships, symbols or forms with interesting verbalisations and/or graphic components" (cited in Tahta et al., 1981, p.44). Similarly, some scholarship argues that poetry can be viewed as mathematics, with poems serving as mnemonic devices and word problems serving as a means to present and explore mathematical concepts (Triandafillidis, 2006; Sinclair & Higginson, 2007). It is notable that modern poets use numbers, analogy, and rhythm to invoke mathematical concepts. Their work has significantly provoked mathematical poetry.

The Evolution of Mathematical Poetry

I keep reflecting on the definition offered in *Against Infinity*, and I wonder, does mathematical poetry have to be a way of explaining/understanding mathematical concepts? Student A incorporates mathematical language into his poetry, while Student B focuses solely on personal stories and feelings. As I traced the answer, I came across "The Colors of Math," a mathematical poem written by the mathematician Karaali (2013, 2014), which portrays her personal experience with mathematics and explains her mathematical process.

sniffing red nose
 blood on your manuscript
 red like anger red like hate
 —Would you like some carrot cake?
 damn coffee!
 burn your fingers stain your notepad
 it HAS to get muddy and brown before it blooms

She didn't use any mathematical term; but "the colours just came one by one, and the words just followed" (Karaali, 2014, p.44) naturally, just like her emotions.

Moving beyond the boundaries of mathematical terms included in mathematical poetry, we should acknowledge one's personal experiences and emotions as they explore the intersections of mathematics and poetry. When mathematicians try to explain why they are so drawn to the field they have dedicated themselves to, they often emphasize the emotional aspect, and in doing so, they discover a sense of "poetry" within mathematics (Tahta et al., 1981). Poetry writing naturally soothes human beings' emotions, hence the combination of aesthetic values and emotional expressiveness in poetry writing serves to promote imagination and meaning construction in mathematics (Jean, 1989; Campos & Saraiva, 2019).

Concluding Remarks

The purpose of this article is to demonstrate that students' emotions are not separate from their mathematical work; in fact, they can be a powerful and integral part of the mathematics learning journey. According to DeBellis and Goldin (2006), affective aspects such as emotions are connected to problem solving and mathematics competence. Mathematical poetry serves as a way for students to process their emotions and connect them to their mathematical work. Some students explicitly incorporate mathematical language into their poetry, like Student A, while others focus on personal stories and leave the mathematics implicit, like Student B. In both cases, we can observe how students' mathematical poetry reflects their emotions and passions, and how these emotions and passions influence their mathematical work. Students seamlessly integrate their mathematical poetry and work into one cohesive piece, showcasing how they view mathematics as a humanistic language. It is important to support students in finding the relevance of mathematics by providing opportunities for them to express their emotions in the mathematics classroom. Ultimately, as mathematics instructors, our role is to help students recognize the vitality of mathematics and find joy and meaning in their mathematical endeavors.

Afterword: Dialogue Between Scholars

“Why do I need to learn this?” has become a perennial *philosophical* question posed by math students to teachers. I have actually come to enjoy this question because it at least conveys some emotion: and why shouldn't mathematics connect to students' emotions? I sought answers by inviting emotional and artistic pieces alongside students' final math projects, which motivated me to start this original research.

Having the intuitive faith that the *Journal for Theoretical & Marginal Mathematics Education* (JTM) might be interested in this sort of work, I submitted my first version. Everyone knows how different their first version looks from the final version, but my first version was especially fuzzy. Despite this, Founding Editor Alex Moore saw some kernels in my work and offered his mentorship via Zoom in June 2024. To this day, I find Alex's words echoing in my head when doing my scholarly work: “write to your heart, don't worry about whether others will like it or not.” During summer 2024, I followed that advice. I wrote some days, slept all day some days, wrote in the dawn or in the dark some days, pouring out words when my ideas were flowing and pounding deep in my heart. At the end of July 2024, I resubmitted the manuscript, a manuscript that I would never have been able to bring to life without Alex's mentorship.

Writing to your heart does work! In fall 2024, the open peer review was initiated. The JTM editorial team helped me establish mentorship under Yasmine Abtahi. Yasmine's expertise and insightful feedback shaped this scholarly work. For example, in my draft, I referred to mathematics itself as emotional. However, Yasmine pointed out that poetry is a dynamic and fluid construct; people create various poems based on their imagination and feelings. In contrast, mathematics is different. It is a more structured system of knowledge, with a defined framework. For my revision, I found myself deeply contemplating how to reconcile these two perspectives. This process evoked memories of doing mathematics with my friends in college, and I can still vividly recall the light in the library and the chilly wind of late fall. I then developed the section on the emotional facet of *doing mathematics*, which further evolved my theoretical vision of the humanistic approach to teaching mathematics.

Through this journey, JTM's Editor-in-Chief, David (they/them), constantly reassured me about my work and provided warm support. They encouraged me to submit partial revisions and shared their wisdom on writing a high-quality piece. They coordinated the open review process

and proofed my work. In this supportive and nurturing academic environment, I am deeply grateful to have been seen as an autonomous young colleague rather than just a graduate student still learning how to write.

Last but not least, I want to express myself as an emerging scholar by offering a poem by Apollinaire. Keep trying new things, and have the courage to push boundaries!

“Come to the edge,” he said.
 They said, “We are afraid.”
 “Come to the edge,” he said.
 They came.
 He pushed them.
 And they flew.

—Apollinaire

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